

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONALISM IN FUTURE TEACHERS IN DESIGNING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривают вопросы основные цели эффективного проектирования и организации образовательного процесса будущими учителями, в чём заключается в непрерывном интеллектуальном, духовно-нравственном и физически-эстетическом развитии учащихся, а также в статье идёт речь о дидактических системах, дидактических процессах и дидактических ситуациях и тогда ли.

Ключевые слова: учитель, преподавания, дидактика, эффективное проектирование, креативность, ответственность, толерантность, любознательность, эмпатия, профессиональная компетентность.

Abstract. This article examines the main goals of effective design and organization of the educational process by future teachers, which is the continuous intellectual, spiritual-moral and physical-aesthetic development of students, and the article also talks about didactic systems, didactic processes and didactic situations and then whether.

Key words: teacher, teaching, didactics, effective design, creativity, responsibility, tolerance, curiosity, empathy, professional competence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite the presence in the practice of higher education of various approaches to determining the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition, assessment of the acquisition of professional knowledge by future teachers is carried out on the basis of the level of their mastery of program material. At the same time, attention is paid to the quality of professional knowledge acquired by future teachers. When determining the quality of the level of performance of future teachers, the following is taken into account: a) reproduction of acquired professional knowledge; b) possession of experience in applying them in teaching practice; c) the ability to transfer acquired knowledge to new learning situations, etc.

The main goal of effective design and organization of the educational process by future teachers is the continuous intellectual, spiritual, moral and physical-aesthetic development of students. To achieve educational goals in personality-oriented education, the teacher must conduct research together with students; for this, even in the process of professional training, the teacher must have steadily formed and developed such qualities as creativity, analysis of one's activities, responsibility, tolerance, curiosity, empathy, professional competence, etc.

II. MAIN PART

Didactic systems, didactic processes and didactic situations are the object of the teacher's design, and the design of the educational process is understood as the complex multi-level activity of the teacher in creating and implementing a model of didactic systems and processes by the teacher.

In the professional activity of a teacher in the design of educational subjects, the following interrelated stages can be distinguished: modeling, design, construction. When developing design

skills in students based on self-improvement, one of the main places is occupied by the constructive design method.

To design the process of a specific lesson by future teachers, it is necessary to develop the skills and abilities to develop a design system for a specific didactic process and its implementation.

When determining the professional skills of future teachers, they rely on the following areas: 1) memory restoration of acquired knowledge; 2) application of acquired knowledge in practical activities, in particular when designing a personality-oriented educational process, choosing creative tasks for the purpose of mental development of students; 3) the ability to apply acquired knowledge in non-standard situations, etc.

When learning the experience of designing an educational process, future teachers should also pay attention to the following: 1) imagine the nature of the process of using the knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies available to students; 2) equip them with ways to carry out educational work that allow them to effectively and economically acquire knowledge; 3) be able to characterize the effectiveness of the methods used by students; 4) determining the needs of students to acquire knowledge based on their personal initiative. It is on this basis that one can master the skills of monitoring one's activities in the future and make adjustments to it, know the ways of self-assessment and improvement of students' educational actions.

The didactic project should reflect the following ways of monitoring the level of learning by students: teachers should continuously monitor the level of learning. To do this, they must observe the continuity and continuity of the knowledge presented in the educational process; pay attention to the fact that the criteria for assessing the level of knowledge of students follow the definition of ways of their work with educational material. In the design of the educational process, each criterion must be clearly indicated, and attention must be paid to their application in the general educational process; ensure that the results of monitoring students' knowledge correspond to its final forms and include all smaller forms of control carried out in the lesson. In the project, the resulting forms of control should be clearly demarcated and should not be expanded; monitoring the results of learning is not only the task of the teacher, but it should be evenly distributed among the subjects of the educational process, i.e. between the teacher and students, which should be provided for in the project.

When a future teacher masters the experience of designing the educational process, it is of great importance to master the skills of organizing precisely such situations. To do this, the future teacher must be able to select and design appropriate learning tasks that encourage creative activity in students. Because educational tasks of this type make it possible to predict the continuous development of students and effectively manage this process.

In personality-oriented and educational processes organized on the basis of these approaches, the knowledge acquired by students should be manifested in their practical actions aimed at completing educational tasks. And therefore, future teachers, in the process of monitoring their knowledge, skills and abilities, must have experience in accurately assessing the possibilities of completing educational tasks.

During the lesson design process, a number of requirements must be met to determine the educational material. In particular, future teachers must: 1) analyze in detail the topic being studied, select and systematize educational material in accordance with the topic of the lesson, and pay special attention in this process to optimizing the knowledge acquired by students; 2) clearly

define the educational material to be mastered, presented to students in the lesson, indicate separately, highlighting the knowledge, information, provisions that students must learn, be able to determine on the basis of what educational material it is necessary to form the knowledge, skills and abilities of students; 3) select educational material that serves the development of students' cognitive abilities, and on this basis systematize and include in the composition (structure) of the project the tasks presented to them.

The principles and directions for diagnosing the pedagogical activity of future teachers in designing the educational process based on self-improvement are unique, the theoretical analysis of which is of particular importance for the process of higher pedagogical education. There is a need to use the following types of diagnostics of the pedagogical activities of future teachers to design a personality-oriented educational process: a holistic diagnosis of the pedagogical knowledge and professional skills acquired by future teachers; intermediate diagnostics of the activities of future teachers in designing the educational process; partial diagnostics of the activities of future teachers in designing a personality-oriented educational process; preliminary diagnostics of the activities of future teachers in designing a personality-oriented educational process (diagnosis is carried out mainly through testing and preparation of lesson plans); final diagnostics of the pedagogical activities of future teachers in the design of a personality-oriented educational process.

III. DISCUSSION

When diagnosing the activities of future teachers in designing a personality-oriented educational process, it is necessary to comply with certain requirements: efficiency and accuracy in clarifying the results; ensuring the integrity of the methods used; achieving the importance of formed professional knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies for the effective design of the educational process; ensuring assessment of the performance of future teachers in designing a person-centered educational process based on strict criteria.

In pedagogical activities aimed at studying the quality of skills of future teachers in designing a personality-oriented educational process, a number of methods were used: 1. Methods that serve to determine the psychological characteristics of the professional activities of future teachers. 2. Methods that serve to diagnose the professional pedagogical activities of future teachers in designing the educational process. 3. Methods for diagnosing the results of research activities of future teachers. 4. Diagnostic methods used to determine the results of future teachers' activities in designing a personality-oriented educational process. 5. Methods that serve to determine the psychological characteristics of the professional activity learned by future teachers.

Using these methods, preliminary observation activities are carried out. Along with this, these methods are used to determine the professional interests of students and analyze the initial manifestations of design activities. It is also possible to use these methods to determine the dynamics of future teachers' activities in designing a personality-oriented educational process.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the process of monitoring the level of development of skills in designing a personality-oriented educational process of future teachers should be organized in compliance with a number of requirements. These are: 1. The observation process is focused on a specific goal, while students are observed to have developed skills in designing a personality-oriented educational process. 2. Planned implementation of the monitoring process; Moreover, before the start of observation, it is advisable to identify specific tasks, plan indicators, ways to eliminate

detected deficiencies, gaps, errors, and plan expected results. 3. Observation is an independent process; in the design of the educational process, students demonstrate independent thinking skills. 4. Observation is a natural pedagogical process; observation should be carried out on the basis of an analysis of the activities of future teachers in designing personality-oriented educational 5. Sequence of the observation process; observation of the dynamics of process design skills development. The educational process of students must be carried out on a systematic basis. 6. Objectivity of the observation process; the observer-professor-teacher, to substantiate his assumptions, must find arguments that serve as an objective assessment of the activities of future teachers in designing a personality-oriented educational process. 7. Expressive nature of observation; the development of future teachers' skills in designing a personality-oriented educational process should be clearly expressed in the results of observational activities.

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